

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART V. THE ESSENTIAL OIL FROM
THE OLEO-RESIN OF *HARDWICKIA PINNATA*

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The essential oil from the oleo-resin of *Hardwickia pinnata* has been shown to consist of humulene (α -caryophyllene), β -caryophyllene and a cadinenic sesquiterpene

Hardwickia pinnata (N. O. Caesalpiniaceae) is a very large and handsome tree found in the evergreen forests of Western Ghats from South Kanara to Travancore. It is also known as the Malabar Mahogany (*Kanada*: Yennemara; *Tamil*: Enneykolavu; *Malayalam*: Shurali; *Marathi*: Anjana). It grows to a height of about 100 ft. with a trunk of about 4 to 8 ft. in diameter. Its wood is moderately hard and yields a valuable timber: the sapwood is spacious and the heartwood is dark red or reddish brown, exuding a red, sticky resin (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 2nd Ed., p. 882; Iyer and Sudborough, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1918-20, 2, 29).

The tree, when tapped, yields a dark oleo-resin. The yield of the resin is about 4 to 16 gallons for a single tree. Sometimes a tree is found which yields no oil at all (Trotter, *Manual of Indian Forest Utilization*', 1940; p. 289). Though the oleo-resin has the smell and taste of Copaiba, its characteristics are sufficiently distinct to prevent any confusion (Hooper, *Pharm. J.*, 1907, 24, 4).

The balsam of *Hardwickia* has been used in India for the treatment of Gonorrhoea (Kirtikar and Basu, *loc. cit.*). The resin exuding from the heartwood is used for dressing the sores of elephants (Rama Rao, "Flowering Plants of Travancore", 1914, p. 142).

According to Weigel (*Phar. Zentr.*, 1906, 47, 773), the oleo-resin contains 48.5% of volatile oil, 48.3% of resin acids and 3.2% of resene. Schimmel and Co. (Reports, April 1905, and April 1907) got 44% of the oil. Iyer and Sudborough determined the percentage of the volatile oil as 43 to 47%. The latter authors prepared caryophyllene alcohol from the oil by Wallach and Walker's method (*Annalen*, 1892, 271, 288). They also prepared a nitrosochloride of m.p. 161° (α -caryophyllene nitrosochloride, m.p. 175°), and a nitrosate, m.p. 153-54° (α -caryophyllene nitrosate, m.p. 162°) and concluded that the oil chiefly consisted of α -caryophyllene and that the β -caryophyllene was absent. But as is evident from the comparison of the m.p. of the derivatives given above, their derivatives were not sufficiently pure and as such their conclusion about the presence of α -caryophyllene was based on unsound grounds. Further, their statement about the absence of β -caryophyllene is erroneous in view of the facts now established.

In order to study the constituents of the volatile oil, we have steam-distilled two lots of the oleo-resin obtained from the Tinnevely district in May, 1946 and October, 1947. It

has been found that the yields of the essential oil and the relative proportions of the chief constituents vary considerably with the season. The first sample gave us only 26% of the oil, which boiled over a comparatively wide range. The second specimen yielded 48.3% of oil consisting mostly of the lower-boiling sesquiterpenes. The essential oil obtained from the 2nd lot of the oleo-resin has been investigated fully.

The oil has a characteristic resinous odour and a pungent bitter taste. The oil as obtained on steam-distillation from a large copper still has a clear, green colour, but the redistilled oil is colorless. Its various constants are given in Table I and have been compared to those recorded by other investigators.

The oil on careful and repeated fractionation furnished six fractions. The physical properties of the various fractions obtained are recorded in Table II. A survey of these properties indicates that the oil consists entirely of bicyclic sesquiterpenes. This has been confirmed by the analyses of the separate fractions.

Fraction I, which constitutes about 80% of the oil, has been shown to consist essentially of β -caryophyllene. The presence of this hydrocarbon was established by the preparation of the characteristic blue nitrosite, m.p. 110° . The m.p. of the compound as given in the literature is 115° (Deussen, *Annalen*, 1907, 366, 13). Since we were unable to raise the m.p. of our product, an authentic sample of β -caryophyllene nitrosite was prepared from genuine caryophyllene (B.D.H.) which also melted at 110° , and did not depress the m.p. of our product. The fraction also yielded β -caryophyllene alcohol on hydration with Bertram-Walbaum reagent. Further, the presence of the hydrocarbon was confirmed by the preparation of caryophyllene dihydrochloride in a 60% yield. The physical constants, especially the optical rotation, of the fraction III agree more closely with those recorded for β -caryophyllene. This fraction yielded the dihydrochloride in practically the same yield, but the nitrosite was obtained in about double the yield. This indicates that probably the fraction I contains another strongly laevo-rotatory hydrocarbon capable of yielding the same dihydrochloride. It is not unlikely that some γ -caryophyllene is present in the oil, but its presence could not be confirmed by the preparation of its nitrosochloride.

Fig. 1

TABLE I

Constants.	Present sample.	Schimmel and Co. (loc. cit.)	Iyer and Sudborough (loc. cit.) Travancore.	Mysore.
<i>d</i>	0.9045 ³⁰ °*	0.90621 ⁶ °	0.931 ¹⁴ °	0.9081 ⁶ °
<i>n</i>	1.4949 ³⁰ °*	—	1.500 ²⁰ °	1.500 ²⁰ °
[α] _D	-9.4	+7.42°	-1.72°	-7.86°
Acid value	Nil	0.85	Trace	Trace
Sapon. value	Nil	2.88	Nil	Nil
Acetyl value	Nil	—	12.6	1.4

Ruzicka and Zimmermann (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1935, 18, 219) made the interesting observation that the caryophyllene mixture as obtained from clove oil was capable of reacting with maleic anhydride in benzene to yield a crystalline adduct (m. p. 98°) corresponding to about 50% of the terpene. Since the chief constituent of the caryophyllenes is supposed to be β -caryophyllene, it is considered likely that the product has originated from this hydrocarbon, which, however, does not contain a conjugated system of double bonds. A careful reinvestigation of the problem by Ruzicka, Plattner and Balla (*ibid.*, 1941, 24, 1219) revealed that the compound is probably formed by diene synthesis by addition to a relatively strongly laevo-rotatory monocyclic sesquiterpene. They examined several different samples of caryophyllene and found that the yields of the adduct were highly variable, and that samples giving higher yields of the dihydrochloride gave poor yields of the maleic anhydride addition product.

The reaction of maleic anhydride with fraction I has also been studied. But the hydrocarbon did not give the product of m. p. 98°. Instead, another crystalline product of m. p. 179-80° was isolated in a poor yield. The substance is under investigation. This supports Ruzicka's results that the adduct of m. p. 98° is not derived from β -caryophyllene.

Fraction V does not yield any picrate-forming material on dehydrogenation with selenium and also does not give the blue nitrosite. The fraction consists chiefly of humulene (α -caryophyllene), as shown by the preparation of the crystalline nitroso-chloride and nitrosate.

Fraction VI gave cadalene and a trace of an unidentified azulene on dehydrogenation with selenium. *l*-Cadinene dihydrochloride was obtained in a poor yield by passing dry HCl gas through its ethereal solution. The fraction is slightly dextro-rotatory and does not give the characteristic colour reaction of cadinene. The cadinenic hydrocarbon present in this fraction may be either *d*-cadinene or some other sesquiterpene capable of giving cadinene dihydrochloride.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

The Oleo-resin.—The oleo-resin was collected by the courtesy of the Forest Range Officer, Ambasamudrum, Tinnevely, in August 1947 and was received by us in October,

1947. The specimen was a thick, viscid liquid of a dark brown (almost black) colour. When viewed in thin layers, the oleo-resin looked transparent and was of a greenish yellow colour. It had a characteristic odour which was not unpleasant.

Fractionation of the Essential Oil

The oleo-resin (29 lbs.) was steam-distilled from a large copper still, when 14 lbs. (48.3%) of a light green oil were obtained. The oil was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled from an ordinary Claisen's flask under vacuum. The oil was obtained as a colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 100° - $105^{\circ}/2$ mm. (125° - $129^{\circ}/10$ mm.). The various constants of the redistilled oil, as recorded in Table I, were determined by standard procedures. The oil was carefully fractionated in vacuum first at 2 mm. The various fractions, thus obtained, were then systematically and repeatedly fractionated at 30-40 mm. in order to have sharper cuts. A final distillation of each fraction was carried out at 2 mm. over sodium. The results of the fractionation are given in Table II.

A fractionating column of the partial-condensation take-off type, as illustrated in Fig. 1, was used. Various types of packings, including single-turn copper helices made from 18 B.S. gauge copper wire, were tried, but flooding could not be controlled; hence the column was indented (Vigreux type). Asbestos rope $\frac{3}{4}$ " in diameter was wound round the column which was finally covered with several rounds of asbestos paper, to serve as insulation. The column is a slight modification of the one described by Thompson ("Organic Syntheses", Vol. XX, p. 96; cf. Morton, "Laboratory Technique in Organic Chemistry", pp. 73-97). The column was operated at a maximum reflux ratio so that there was just no flooding. The rate of distillation was maintained at about 0.5 c.c./min. The reflux ratio was adjusted by the manipulation of the dephlegmator and by wrapping or unwrapping some cotton wool over the portion of the column just above the insulation. The oil was heated in a metal bath with proper control of the bath temperature.

The oil (3000 g.) on fractionation gave seven fractions (vide Table II) on which different physical measurements were made.

TABLE II

No.	B.p.	Weight.	% Yield.	d_{30}^{30}	n_D^{30}	$[\alpha]_D^{24}$	MR _b .
I	$150^{\circ}/36$ mm. $100^{\circ}/2$	233.8 g.	77.9	0.8976	1.4940	-10.5	66.09
II	$150-52^{\circ}/36$	86.0	2.9	—	—	—	—
III	$152-53^{\circ}/36$	176.0	5.9	0.8990	1.4955	-9.3	66.17
IV	$153-55^{\circ}/36$	20.0	0.6	—	—	—	—
V	$155-57^{\circ}/36$	93.0	3.1	0.8997	1.4960	-6.0	66.19
VI	$114-15^{\circ}/3$	80.0	2.6	0.9026	1.4990	+0.5	66.32
VII	Residue	80.0	2.6	—	—	—	—
	Loss	127.0	4.2	—	—	—	—

Identification of β -Caryophyllene

The evidence for the identification of β -caryophyllene in *Hardwickia pinnata* oil are summarised in Table III.

The Nitrosite.—The fraction I (10 c. c.) was dissolved in petroleum ether (10.0 c.c., b.p. 60°-80°) and an aqueous saturated solution of sodium nitrite (10.0 c. c.) was added. The mixture was chilled in ice and salt mixture to below -10° and glacial acetic acid (10 c. c.) was introduced slowly under shaking during 10 to 15 minutes. The petroleum ether layer slowly turned blue and towards the end blue needles started separating out. The reaction mixture was kept in the ice-bath for another 15 minutes and the crystals that separated out were filtered off and washed with a little petrol and further purified by recrystallising twice from dilute alcohol in long, blue needles, m.p. 110° with effervescence. Yield from fraction I, 1.4 to 1.6 g. (10-12%); fraction III gave nearly double this yield.

Further recrystallisations of the product from dilute alcohol or petroleum (b.p. 40°-60°) failed to raise the melting point.

TABLE III

Properties.	β -Caryophyllene.	Fraction I.	Fraction III.
B.p.	103°-103.5°/4 mm*.	100.0°/2 mm.	102-103°/2 mm.
Density	d_{20}^{20} , 0.9075*	d_{20}^{20} , 0.8976	d_{20}^{20} , 0.8990
Ref. index	n_D^{20} , 1.4995**	n_D^{20} , 1.4940	n_D^{20} , 1.4955
Optical rotation [α] _D	-8.16*	-10.5	-9.3
%C	88.16 (calc.)	88.01	88.23
%H	11.84 (calc.)	11.90	11.75
M.p. of nitrosite	115.0°; (110.0°)**	110.0°	110.0°
M.p. of dihydrochloride	69-70°†	68.9°	68-69°
M.p. of β -caryophyllene alcohol	94-96°††	95-96°	95-96°

* Naves and Perrottet, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1941, 24, 789.

** The m.p. 110° is of the product prepared by the authors from genuine caryophyllene. Deussen (*Annalen*, 1907, 386, 13) has recorded the m.p. as 115°.

† Schreiner and Kremers, *Pharm. Arch.*, 1899, 2, 296; 1902, 5, 164.

†† Wallach and Walker, *Annalen*, 1892, 271, 288; Asahina and Tsukamoto, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1922, 463; *Chem. Abst.*, 1922, 16, 3312.

The mixed melting points of the nitrosite, dihydrochloride and β -caryophyllene alcohol, prepared from genuine caryophyllene (B.D.H.) with the corresponding derivatives prepared from these fractions, were 110° , $68-69^\circ$ and $95-96^\circ$ respectively.

The Dihydrochloride.—The hydrocarbon (10.0 g.) was mixed with anhydrous ether (10 c.c.) and cooled in an ice-salt bath (-20°). The well-cooled solution was saturated with dry HCl gas and the practically colorless solution thus obtained was kept in the freezing mixture for 16 hours. The solvent and the excess of the HCl gas were sucked off in vacuum with a feeble current of dry air being passed through it. The residual syrup was chilled in a freezing mixture (-20°) for $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour with occasional scratching, when the product solidified. This was taken up in 7 c. c. of ether and 15 c. c. of alcohol were added. The clear solution was chilled as before for $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour. The white crystals were filtered off and washed with a little cold alcohol. The product was recrystallised from alcohol and ether in the same way, as white needles, m.p. $68-69^\circ$, yield 50-60%.

β -Caryophyllene Alcohol.—The fraction I (10 g.) was mixed with 98% acetic acid (20 g.) and 50% sulphuric acid (1 g.). The reaction mixture was heated at $50^\circ-60^\circ$ for 8 hours. The dark violet reaction mixture was poured into excess of water and the crude acetyl β -caryophyllene alcohol was extracted with ether and then hydrolysed with alcoholic potash by refluxing for 2 hours. The hydrolysed product was worked up in the usual manner with ether. The solvent was removed and the residue was fractionated in vacuum. The β -caryophyllene alcohol distilled at $120^\circ-125^\circ/1$ mm. The distillate which had crystallised out was recrystallised from petrol ether ($40^\circ-60^\circ$) at 10° to a constant melting point as white silky needles, m.p. $95-96^\circ$ (cf. Bertram and Walbaum, *J. pharm. Chem.*, 1894 ii, 49, 1; Wallach and Walker, *loc. cit.* Asahina and Tsukamoto, *loc. cit.*).

Reaction with Maleic Anhydride.—The fraction did not give the colour reaction with diazotised *p*-nitroaniline (Fieser's test for conjugation: Fieser and Campbell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 168; cf. Goodway and West, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1855). β -Caryophyllene as isolated from clove oil gives an orange-brown colour in a few minutes (Naves and Perrottet, *loc. cit.*).

A mixture of the terpene (25 g.), maleic anhydride (15 g.) and dry benzene (75 c. c.) was refluxed for 24 hours. A clear yellow solution resulted. The solvent was removed under a slight vacuum and the residue was fractionated at a low pressure. Maleic anhydride distilled over first, followed by the unreacted terpene (18 g., 72%). A higher boiling fraction, b.p. $180^\circ-200^\circ/2$ mm. (4.0 g.) was obtained and a polymer was left in the flask. The fraction (b.p. $180^\circ-200^\circ/2$ mm.) was obtained as a syrup which crystallised on trituration with light petrol. The crystals were filtered off and recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and petrol, m.p. $177-80^\circ$. Further recrystallisation from the same mixture of solvents raised the m.p. to $179-80^\circ$ with slight shrinking at $177-78^\circ$. The product was obtained in white silky needles, yield 0.6 g. (cf. Ruzicka, Plattner and Balla, *loc. cit.*).

Identification of Humulene

The evidences for the presence of humulene in the essential oil from *Hardwickia pinnata* oleo-resin are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Properties.	Humniene*.	Fraction V.
R p.	263°-266°	155°-57°/36 mm.
Density	d_{15}° , 0.9001	d_{20}° , 0.8997
Refrac. index	n_D^{20} , 1.5021	n_D^{20} , 1.4960
Optical rotation	Inactive	-6.0
M.p. of nitrosate	163°, 161°	160°
M.p. of nitrosochloride	176°; 174°**	175°
M.p. of nitropiperidide	153°	153°

* Chapman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 87, 54, 780; 1928, 785.

† Simonsen and Todd, *ibid.*, 1942, 191.

The Nitrosate.—The terpene (10 c.c.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and freshly prepared (undistilled) *iso*-amyl nitrite (11.0 c.c.) was added. The resulting green solution was chilled in an ice-salt-bath. A well-cooled mixture of glacial acetic acid (10 c. c.) and conc. nitric acid (d 1.42; 10 c. c.) was then slowly added to the above solution with shaking. The temperature was not allowed to go beyond 0°. After 15 minutes 50 c. c. of alcohol were added and the clear green solution was left aside in the ice-bath for 3 to 4 hours. The white solid which had separated out was filtered off, washed with some cold alcohol and dried. The product was recrystallised several times from a mixture of benzene and alcohol as fine silky needles, m.p. 160° with decomposition.

Nitrosochloride.—A well-cooled alcoholic solution of HCl gas (20 c. c.) was added slowly to a chilled mixture of the hydrocarbon (20 c. c.), absolute alcohol (20 c. c.), ethyl acetate (20 c. c.) and *iso*-amyl nitrite (20 c. c.). The deep bluish green mixture was left in the ice-bath for an hour and was then kept at room temperature for another 2 hours. The white crystalline solid was filtered off and washed with ice-cold alcohol. The product was repeatedly crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and benzene till the m.p. became constant. The product was obtained in colorless prisms, m.p. 175° (decomp.), yield 5.0%.

The Nitropiperidide was prepared by the action of piperidine on the nitrosochloride in the usual manner. The compound was recrystallised from dilute alcohol as fine white needles, m.p. 153°.

Presence of a Cadinenic Sesquiterpene

Dehydrogenation.—The fraction VI (2.0 g.) and selenium (4.0 g.) were heated together at 300°-315° for 32 hours when the evolution of hydrogen selenide had practically

ceased. In the beginning the reflux slowly acquired a deep blue colour, which vanished towards the end. The product was worked up in the usual manner. The cadalene was identified as its picrate, m.p. 114-15°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample remained undepressed.

Dihydrochloride.—The fraction VI (1 c. c.) was dissolved in dry ether (1 c. c.) and saturated with dry HCl gas at below 0° and the mixture kept at 0° for 24 hours. The ether and the excess gas were then sucked off and the residue was taken up in 1 c. c. of ethyl acetate. The solution was chilled to -10° and seeded with a speck of cadinene dihydrochloride when crystals began to separate out. After sometime the product was filtered off and recrystallised from ethyl acetate in white needles, m. p. 117-18°. Cadinene dihydrochloride, m.p. 117-118°, did not depress the m.p.

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